

Supplementary Material

Table S1. Predicted reaction rate constants of proposed reaction scheme for AC with their 95 % confidence interval

Reaction rate constant*	AC				± 95 % confidence interval			
	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C
k ₁	4.85E-04	1.31E-03	7.79E-03	3.03E-02	1.55E-04	3.28E-04	1.43E-03	7.14E-03
k ₂	2.27E+01	1.40E-02	8.53E-02	2.76E-01	8.20E+02	1.52E-01	2.40E-01	3.21E-01
k ₃	2.82E-02	2.88E-07	6.36E-02	4.16E-02	3.41E+02	1.79E-01	2.11E-01	1.39E-01
k ₄	6.57E-11	1.20E-02	6.59E-11	2.25E-14	7.33E+04	2.92E-01	1.17E-01	4.60E-02
k ₅	2.50E-14	7.03E-09	1.98E-02	4.24E-02	3.67E-02	1.73E-02	1.81E-02	2.25E-02
k ₆	4.12E-14	2.83E-14	4.36E-10	6.61E-09	3.51E+02	1.66E-01	1.77E-01	1.90E-01
k ₇	4.08E-14	2.97E-14	8.74E-10	4.05E-02	7.33E+04	2.95E-01	1.20E-01	6.64E-02
k ₈	4.04E-14	1.01E-08	3.63E-03	1.14E-03	5.80E+07	6.21E-02	4.50E-02	4.66E-03
k ₉	2.23E-06	9.05E-03	3.69E-02	1.44E-01	9.81E-02	5.04E-03	1.32E-02	3.00E-02

* The unit of kinetic rate constant is min⁻¹ for **k₁-k₈** and L²(mol C)⁻²min⁻¹ for **k₉**.

Table S2. Predicted reaction rate constants of proposed reaction scheme for MC with their 95 % confidence interval

Reaction rate constant*	MC				± 95% confidence interval			
	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C
k ₁	2.63E-04	1.39E-03	1.12E-02	1.35E-01	2.37E-04	2.50E-04	2.16E-03	4.49E-02
k ₂	2.96E-02	1.75E-02	2.81E-02	1.30E-01	9.15E-01	4.01E-01	5.70E-02	7.56E-02
k ₃	4.89E-09	6.85E-11	2.35E-02	3.69E-02	1.14E-03	3.73E-01	6.22E-02	4.82E-02
k ₄	4.32E-14	2.82E-02	2.11E-11	5.93E-14	3.93E+01	7.01E-01	1.26E-01	5.79E-02
k ₅	3.78E-14	2.59E-14	2.86E-02	1.50E-01	1.49E-01	2.21E-02	3.07E-02	6.36E-02
k ₆	6.50E-14	1.47E-10	5.22E-13	4.95E-02	7.80E-01	2.40E-01	6.55E-02	7.26E-02
k ₇	2.79E-14	2.56E-14	2.12E-12	2.34E-10	3.92E+01	5.42E-01	1.32E-01	8.65E-02
k ₈	2.46E+00	2.56E-14	3.55E-03	5.78E-04	2.99E+03	2.60E-02	2.61E-02	2.29E-03
k ₉	1.10E-05	1.56E-02	4.61E-02	7.80E-02	3.04E-01	3.97E-03	2.09E-02	7.82E-02

* The unit of kinetic rate constant is min⁻¹ for **k₁-k₈** and L²(mol C)⁻²min⁻¹ for **k₉**.

Table S3. Missing reaction rate constants of proposed scheme in AC and MC at different temperatures.

Reaction rate constant*	AC				MC			
	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C	180 °C	200 °C	220 °C	240 °C
k ₃	2.82E-02	2.88E-07	6.36E-02	4.16E-02	4.89E-09	6.85E-11	2.35E-02	3.69E-02
k ₄	6.57E-11	1.20E-02	6.59E-11	2.25E-14	4.32E-14	2.82E-02	2.11E-11	5.93E-14
k ₆	4.12E-14	2.83E-14	4.36E-10	6.61E-09	6.50E-14	1.47E-10	5.22E-13	4.95E-02
k ₇	4.08E-14	2.97E-14	8.74E-10	4.05E-02	2.79E-14	2.56E-14	2.12E-12	2.34E-10
k ₈	4.04E-14	1.01E-08	3.63E-03	1.14E-03	2.46E+00	2.56E-14	3.55E-03	5.78E-04

* The unit of kinetic rate constant is min⁻¹ for **k₃-k₈**.

Figure S1. Arrhenius plots of kinetic rate constants (k)

Figure S2. Concentration of products from AC at a) 180 °C b) 200 °C c) 220 °C d) 240 °C and from MC at e) 180 °C f) 200 °C g) 220 °C h) 240 °C as a function of reaction time (○: Cellulose, □: Sugars, * : Furans, △: Acids, ◇: Char, +: Residues, solid lines: model predicted yield, dot lines: predicted pyrochar, and dash lines: predicted hydrochar).